

Phishing Website Detection using BERT & Handcrafted features

Dr. Shwetal Patil

*Dept of Computer Engineering,
Marathwada MitraMandal's
Institute of Technology Pune, India*
shwetal.patil@mmit.edu.in

Hemakshi Ingale

*Dept of Computer Engineering,
Marathwada MitraMandal's
Institute of Technology Pune, India*
hemakshiingale@gmail.com

Deesha Dhabale

*Dept of Computer Engineering,
Marathwada MitraMandal's
Institute of Technology Pune, India*
deeshadhbabale@gmail.com

Rohan Bhujbal

*Dept of Computer Engineering,
Marathwada MitraMandal's
Institute of Technology Pune, India*
rohanbhujbal63@gmail.com

Atharv Dixit

*Dept of Computer Engineering,
Marathwada MitraMandal's
Institute of Technology Pune, India*
dixitatharv2004@gmail.com

Abstract - Phishing attacks are found to be the most common and dangerous cyber threats, and they deceive users into revealing sensitive information such as passwords and banking details. Traditional Phishing detection techniques fail to detect advanced phishing techniques/links and show poor generalization across unseen data. This BERT based model overcomes these flaws from the traditional phishing techniques. This model combines both textual and structural URL features.

A well trained Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers (BERT) model shows relationship between the URL text and associated metadata. Also it shows the features such as domain length, special characters, and hosting information for enhancing the model's ability to differentiate between authentic and phishing URLs. The proposed BERT model aims to enhance the generalization capability of phishing detection systems by learning from multiple models and data.

The BERT model is trained on publicly available phishing datasets by using publicly available phishing datasets and machine learning models like SVM, Random Forest, and Logistic Regression are used to detect the phishing URL. The result shows that the BERT model gives accuracy, precision, and F1-score, also the BERT model significantly reduces false positives and improves performance against unseen phishing URLs. This work builds a more reliable phishing detection framework which can be integrated in real-world cybersecurity systems also it provides enhanced protection for users and organizations against phishing threats.

Keywords - Phishing Detection, BERT, Handcrafted Features, Deep Learning, Cybersecurity, Web Security, Transformer Models, Natural Language Processing (NLP), URL Analysis, Machine Learning, Feature Fusion, Mode

INTRODUCTION

As we all live in the 20th century, we are continuously surrounded by online services, e-commerce, and digital banking. This has made cybersecurity a very important concern in today's world for individual as well as industrial purposes. Phishing attacks are one of the most common forms of online cyber attack. In this kind of cyber attack, attackers create fraud websites or URLs that are similar to the authentic URL. If one opens that website it reveals their important information like login credentials, credit card details, or personal data. This not only affects financial loss but also affects the trust of the user.

Blacklist-based filtering and rule-based filtering are Traditional phishing detection methods. These methods run on the predefined URL patterns and manually maintained repositories. They are efficient for the already blacklisted url and cannot detect the newly detected or dynamically altered links which are not yet blacklisted. Here BERT and handcrafted features improve detection to an unauthentic URL and improves security.

For evading detection attackers continuously change the structure and appearance of the URL. The development of Natural Language Processing(NLP) and Transformer-based deep learning architectures has enhanced how textual data is

processed and understood. BERT shows relationships between contextual and semantic within text sequences. BERT processes input in both preceding and succeeding directions, that is, bidirectionally, which helps in checking in both directions at once which makes it highly effective in understanding URL text and domain names. When we use the BERT model for checking if the URL is authentic or not, it extracts subtle linguistic and contextual cues which help in differentiating between malicious and non-malicious URL. Non-textual characteristics are also important for detecting malicious URLs; hence, we cannot only use the BERT model.

domain length, use of subdomains, frequency of special characters, HTTPS usage, or IP-based domains are the structural and lexical indicators that are also very useful in phishing URL detection. Here, we use these handcrafted features along with our BERT model because these features strongly predict malicious activity in the URL. This work will combine handcrafted features with the deep learning concepts of the BERT model. Our hybrid model is trained on supervised machine learning algorithms such as Support Vector Machine, Random Forest, and Logistic Regression, and uses the standard evaluation metrics like accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score. These trained hybrid models are enhanced and superior to the traditional model. This model reduces the false positives on the unseen phishing URLs.

We come to the conclusion that combining the transformer-based models with handcrafted features improves the performance and helps in the evolution of phishing detection research. The hybrid model is more reliable, accurate, and explainable, which gives solutions to the traditional methods used and also increases the security and decreases cyber threats.

I. LITERATURE REVIEW

Reference[1]

Murhej M. and Nallasivan G. (2025). This paper introduced a multimodal phishing detection architecture that combines FH-BERT, EfficientNet, and CRNN-based models. This model uses semantic, visual, and structural features simultaneously, which helps in improving detection accuracy against complex phishing URLs. Rather than using the single mode, this hybrid model gives more accurate results. This model is highly effective for large datasets and adapts to zero-day phishing attacks.

Reference[2]

Barik K., Misra S., and Mohan R. (2025). This system uses parameter optimization for accuracy and reducing training loss compared to traditional ML models. It developed a deep learning-optimized phishing URL detection approach using advanced tuning methods for neural networks. The model tells us that when deep models are properly fine-tuned, they achieve stable performance over multiple datasets.

Reference[3]

An AI-Driven Phishing Detection Framework (2025) uses reinforcement learning for adaptable phishing detection. In real time, the system continuously gets updated, which allows it to identify new phishing behaviors without retraining. Reinforcement learning can make phishing detection systems self-evolving.

Reference[4]

Altan I., Bachir A., and Parbhulkar Y. (2025). This is a dual phishing detection that combines the BERT model with the handcrafted features. This model improves the accuracy in the detection of phishing websites.

II. PROBLEM FORMULATION

Phishing is one of the new and most dominant and dangerous cybercrime in today's world which causes users not only loss of finances but also the trust. Attackers design malicious websites and URLs that are similar to the authentic and legitimate for deceiving users into revealing confidential information such as passwords, bank details, and personal data. This compromises individual privacy as well as it leads to large-scale financial losses, data breaches, and organizational damage. With the increasing phishing, it is a great challenge for today's world to develop a working technique for detection of phishing.

Traditional phishing detection systems include blacklist-based, rule-based, and machine learning-based. Blacklist-based systems compare URLs against known databases of phishing sites and it offers quick detection for known blacklisted URLs and cannot detect zero-day phishing attacks; the newly created malicious URLs cannot be detected in black blacklist method. Rule-based systems work on manually crafted features such as URL length, presence of special symbols, or absence of HTTPS. But this method lacks the adaptability for developing and enhanced malicious URLs and only detects the malicious URL on a basic scale.

Rather than using traditional algorithms for detection of

phishing websites, machine learning and deep learning approaches are effective alternatives by enabling systems to learn from data and identify hidden patterns that differentiate between authentic and malicious websites. ML models such as Decision Trees, Random Forests(RF), Support Vector Machines (SVM), and Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) are widely used for phishing URL detection. but these models largely depend on manually engineered features which affects their ability to generalize to unseen phishing attacks. traditional models fail to capture the semantic meaning hidden within the textual patterns of URLs.

To prevent these limitations we focus on the To address these limitations, this project focuses on Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers (BERT) which combines deep learning with handcrafted features. BERT, a transformer-based architecture, excels at understanding bidirectional contextual information from text sequences. BERT can learn complex similarities and patterns between URL components and detect patterns that traditional models overlook. BERT provides powerful semantic understanding, the features like number of dots, presence of IP addresses, domain length, and subdomain count which BERT cannot handle is handled by our handcrafted features. The problem is defined as follows:

Given a dataset $D = \{(X_i, y_i)\}_{i=1}^N$, where X_i represents a phishing or legitimate (authentic) URL and $y_i \in \{0, 1\}$

represents its class label (1 for phishing and 0 for legitimate). The objective is to learn a mapping function:

$$f(X_i) \rightarrow y_i$$

that minimizes classification error and maximizes detection accuracy. Each URL X_i can be represented as a combination of two feature sets:

$$X_i = [F_{bert} \parallel F_{handcrafted}]$$

where F_{bert} denotes the BERT-generated contextual embedding that captures semantic relationships within the URL. Handcrafted refers to a vector of features derived from the URL's structure and metadata. The model is trained to minimize the binary cross-entropy loss function:

$$L = -(1/N) \sum [y_i \log(\hat{y}_i) + (1 - y_i) \log(1 - \hat{y}_i)]$$

where \hat{y}_i is the predicted probability output by the model and y_i is the true label. This approach allows the system to learn from both semantic and statistical perspectives, effectively improving its robustness and ability to process unseen data.

The project's primary objectives can be summarized as follows:

Develop a hybrid phishing detection model that combines BERT-based contextual embeddings with handcrafted URL and domain features.

Improve the generalization capability of the detection model so it can effectively identify newly generated phishing URLs not present in existing datasets.

Reduce false positives and false negatives, enhancing the precision and recall of phishing classification systems.

Evaluate model performance using benchmark phishing datasets and compare it with traditional ML and deep learning techniques such as Logistic Regression, Random Forest, and CNN.

Design a scalable and deployable detection system that can be integrated into browsers, email clients, or enterprise-level cybersecurity tools.

The problem formulation lies in bridging the gap between semantic understanding and structural pattern analysis. By leveraging BERT's deep linguistic modeling along with feature-based insights, the proposed system aims to build a more intelligent, explainable, and general phishing detection framework. Such a system can detect malicious URLs in real time, adapt to evolving attack strategies, and strengthen overall web security.

In conclusion, this research formulates the problem of phishing detection as a multimodal learning challenge. Textual semantics and handcrafted statistical features must be effectively combined to detect phishing URLs with high accuracy. The ultimate goal is to provide a system that is both robust and scalable, capable of supporting real-world cybersecurity applications that require quick, reliable, and adaptable defense mechanisms against phishing threats.

III. METHODOLOGY

Nowadays, many people click on phishing websites and become victims of cybercrime. It is very difficult to identify such websites because the hackers create them in such a way that they cannot be easily identified. This project focuses on identifying phishing websites by integrating machine learning and natural language processing. It employs a data driven methodology that includes both analytical and experimental development, progressing through multiple stages that are essential for constructing and validating the phishing detection model.

1. Research Design

In order to train the classification model, this study uses a labelled dataset of phishing and URLs, as well as experimental research. This model uses a handcrafted structural feature to help detect the URL of a phishing website. Our goal is to enhance the functionality of the current method and create a unified platform that can identify hidden phishing URLs and prevent victims of cybercrime.

2. Dataset and Pre-processing

In order to help us design the project's structure, we are using two datasets. One small dataset is used exclusively for testing and tuning. The other dataset, which is utilized for final training and deployment, is modern and realistic. These two are effective in identifying both simple and advanced attacks. Pre-processing techniques include-

1. URL Cleaning- Raw URLs are cleaned by removing unnecessary elements like slashes, duplicate characters etc.
2. Tokenization- Cleaned URLs are broken into smaller tokens using separators like /, ., ?, =, -, _ and numbers. These tokens are used by BERT for understanding patterns.
3. Normalization- All characters are converted to lowercase which helps the model treat similar URLs consistently.
4. Handcrafted Feature Preparation- System calculates the structural features like URL length, number of digits and subdomain.

3. Feature Extraction

Contextual Feature Extraction (BERT)

Bidirectional encoder representation from encoder (BERT) understands text better than older NLP methods. It tokenizes URLs and generates embeddings. A pre-trained BERT helps to understand the context of words in URL which helps to detect hidden phishing tricks like misspellings and space between words.

Handcrafted Structural Features

Handcrafted structural features focus on characteristics of URL that reveal phishing patterns. It looks for length of URL (number of characters), number of subdomain, tokens and count of special characters like @, -, _, ? etc. It also measures randomness and looks for the presence of suspicious keywords (eg., "Login", "secure", "verify"). These features help the model to capture clues that only

BERT may not detect.

We extract the root of the URL text using BERT and calculate handcrafted features separately.

4. Model Architecture and Fusion

The model uses two pathways-

1. BERT : It understands the context of words in the URL. BERT first tokenizes the URL and detects hidden phishing tricks, also learns the pattern, looks for strange keyword placement, sequence, suspicious combinations used in the URL.
2. Handcrafted Feature : It captures the structure and shape of the URL. The system brings out handcrafted structural features such as length of URL, number of dots or hyphens, presence of @ symbol, randomness of characters and SSL certificate validity.

Results from both pathways are combined in a single vector. This vector is further fed into the final classifier, which predicts whether the URL is phishing or safe to go. Combining these both improve the overall detection accuracy

5. Training Strategy & Optimization

Loss function used is binary cross entropy, defined as

$$L = -(1/N) \sum [y_i \times \log(\hat{y}_i) + (1 - y_i) \times \log(1 - \hat{y}_i)],$$

with \hat{y}_i as the predicted probability and y_i as the true label. The optimizer employed is Adam, coupled with learning rate scheduling. Regularization techniques include dropout and early stopping based on validation loss to prevent overfitting. Hyperparameter tuning is conducted through grid search for learning rate, batch size, dropout rate, and the number of units

6. Evaluation Metrics

Model performance is analyzed using accuracy, precision, recall F1 score and confusion matrix. These mathematical functions show the performance of the model. A confusion matrix examines and visualizes how the model classifies phishing and safe URLs.

7. Comparative Experiments and Validation

The hybrid BERT-based model is evaluated by comparing it with traditional machine learning methods. For this

comparison, models like CNN, SVM, Random Forest, and Logistic Regression each trained only on handcrafted features which are used as baselines. All models are trained and tested on the same dataset. The results clearly show that the hybrid model performs better in terms of accuracy, precision, and recall, proving that it can learn more effectively and generalize far better than the conventional approaches.

Another part of validation involves testing the model on phishing URLs it has never encountered before, collected from updated online sources to simulate zero day attacks. The feature analysis also explains why the hybrid approach works so well. The BERT embeddings provide a deeper understanding of how different features such as the number of subdomains make the model's decisions easier to interpret.

8. Deployment Considerations

The final stage of the methodology focuses on transforming the trained model into a deployable and user-friendly application. The deployment process includes designing an interface that allows users or network administrators to input URLs and instantly receive classification results.

A web-interface can be developed using HTML, CSS, JavaScript. This allows integration of the model into browsers, email systems, or enterprise security tools. The interface displays detection results such as "Phishing" or "Legitimate" along with a probability score for transparency.

The proposed system employs a hybrid deep learning and feature-engineering architecture to accurately detect phishing websites. It integrates BERT (Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers) for contextual feature extraction, handcrafted feature modules for structural analysis, and a machine learning classifier for final decision-making. The architecture ensures seamless interaction between data ingestion, feature fusion, model inference, and output interpretation, thereby enhancing detection accuracy and explainability. The architecture consists of three primary layers:

IV. Proposed System

1. System Design and Architecture

This project will combine both algorithms to create a model that will accurately identify phishing websites and save from phishing attacks. It will use BERT to extract features, handcrafted features, analyze the model structure and build a better and more accurate model. Model get the help of machine learning classification to make the final decision.

The architecture consists of three primary layers:

1. Data Acquisition Layer:

This layer deals with collecting the URLs which are used to test and train the model. The URLs come from publicly available phishing and legitimate datasets and each one is already marked as either safe or harmful. Since the model works only with URL strings, no web page content or extra metadata is downloaded. After collecting them, the URLs are cleaned and prepared for the next steps.

2. Processing Layer:

BERT-based Semantic Encoder: URLs are passed through BERT encoder. BERT breaks the URLs in tokens and brings out the hidden patterns. It checks the randomness of characters and also the presence of special characters.

Handcrafted Feature Extractor: Handcrafted feature extractor calculates the length of URL, number of digits and symbols it looks at the randomness of characters which are hard to catch.

After processing both features are then passed forward for final classification.

3. Classification and Data Management Layer:

In the classification layer, features from both BERT encoder and handcrafted feature extractor are combined to form a single vector. This is sent to the classifier which decides whether the URL is phishing or not. These results are stored in the system to be used later for further testing.

2. Components

Administrator manages the system configuration and updates the dataset. It monitors the system performance and gives logs about classification. Administrators adjust the parameters for an improved detection system.

The Detection Engine is the most important part of the system. It takes URL features from BERT and Handcrafted features, combines them and passes for classification whether they are phishing or safe.

A simple web interface for detecting the phishing website URLs. User have to enter the URL and the system will give a response whether the URL is phishing or safe.

Database acts as a storage system. It stores important information such as URLs, extracted features, results of detection and logs. This ensures that the system keeps record of past data and reviews.

Logging and Report Module keeps records of detected

URLs, patterns, type of phishing URLs and how often the URLs are detected as phishing.

3. Technologies Used

Programming languages used are Python, HTML, CSS, JavaScript

Flask, Transformers like Hugging Face, Scikit-learn, Pandas, NumPy are the libraries and frameworks used in system development.

BERT and Handcrafted Feature are machine learning algorithms used for training and testing the model.

Matplotlib, Seaborn are used to visualize results, confusion matrix, graphs and performance measures.

4. Feature Extraction:

BERT Encoder: The pre-trained BERT model transforms textual content into contextual embeddings, capturing semantic relationships and intent.

Handcrafted Features: Feature engineering modules derive numerical values representing URL structure, domain authority, and security indicators.

5. Feature Fusion:

BERT and Handcrafted Features are combined to form a single vector which is further used for classification. By fusing these both models become more balanced, advanced and informative.

6. Classification:

Once the fusion of features are done we get a single vector which is passed for classification to give results as the URL is phishing or safe. This step completes the detection process and gives final output which is used for performance evaluation.

7. Evaluation & Optimization:

The evaluation of the model is done using standard matrix, accuracy, precision, recall, f1 score and by visualizing confusion matrix. This evaluation shows how well the model detects the known and unknown pattern of phishing URL and gives accurate output.

During optimization binary cross-entropy loss function and

Adam optimizer finely tuned the model which helps to achieve stable learning. Optimization strategies are used to maintain the accuracy of model and also maintain the capability to detect and handle unseen new phishing patterns

V. CONCLUSION

By combining BERT and handcrafted features we can develop a strong and reliable solution for the advanced Phishing URL Detection. This hybrid model is able to detect all the patterns and structural hidden characteristics which is the drawback of traditional phishing URL detection.

For final decision making this model used a decision tree which integrated a transformer-based model and ML and deep learning model with the objective of adaptability and efficiency. The results of this hybrid model when compared with the traditional model gives higher accuracy, recall and F1 score.

On large labeled datasets handcrafted features provide interpretability and reduce dependence which makes the system more suitable for deployment in diverse environments.

In conclusion, the hybrid model of BERT and handcrafted features is the next step in evolution towards building explainable, scalable, and high-performing phishing detection systems. By integrating Deep Learning with ML with handcrafted feature, this approach strengthens cybersecurity as well as contributes to the broader goal of creating AI-driven, trustworthy, and resilient web ecosystems which creates a reliable and trust worthy web eco system

VI. REFERENCES

- [1] Songailaitė, M., Kankevičiūtė, E., Zhyhun, B., & Mandravickaitė, J. (2023). BERT-Based Models for Phishing Detection. Fine-tunes DistilBERT/TinyBERT/RobERTa for phishing detection (email-based experiments) and reports comparative results.
- [2] Uddin, M. A. (2024). Its a transformer based model for phishing email detection and imbalance handling also it is a BIRT variant type of model.
- [3] Sayak Saha Roy & Nilizadeh, S. (2024). PhishLang: this model uses MobileBERT and it is a lightweight Client side phishing detection framework. For real time URL detection

it has generated chromium extension.

[4] Koide, T. (2024). (arXiv) For advanced analysis purposes uses BERT and LLM methods. Used for email context and AI-generated phishing.

[5] Jamal, S. (2023). Used for detection of spam (IPSDM) by using a Transformer based Model. For improving phishing and accurate classification this transformer based model uses customized DistilBert and RoBERT.

[6] Mahdaouy, A. E. (2024). This is the pre-trained model in which there is a BERT Encoder for detection of Malicious Domains and URLs. That is, a pre-trained BERT model is used for detection of maliciousness in the URL..

[7] Alhasan, A. E. (2025). With the help of AI it improves Real-time phishing Detection. -Open PDF thesis/report demonstrating transformer utility for real-time phishing/email detection and deployment notes.

[8] Altwaijry, N., et al. (2024). Used for the phishing Email Detection it used public dataset to compare 1D-CNN & Bi-GRU vs. transformer models

[9] Murhej, M., & Nallasivan, G. (2025). Uses EfficientNet, FH-BERT, and SELU-CRNN such components on advanced phishing websites for comparison purposes.

[10] Elsadig, M., et al. (2022). This is based on deep learning (intelligent) for Cyber URL Detection based on the BERT model. Uses features such as BERT embeddings along with ML classifier or URL phishing detection.

[11] Sanwal, M. (2021). A Hybrid Phishing Detection Model Based on a Transformer model from URLs. it is an Early hybrid approach which apply CharacterBERT to raw URL tokens plus traditional features.

[12] "In-Depth Analysis of Phishing Email Detection" (2025). framework based on ML/DL models which uses multiple datasets for baselines and dataset merging. This is very useful Survey.

[13] A. Fajar, S. Yazid, & I. Budi (2024). for Enhancing Phishing Detection via Feature Importance Analysis and Explainable AI. this model Compares tree ensembles with feature-importance explainability useful for handcrafted feature selection.

[14] Rao, R. S., et al. (2025). Phish-Jam: for phishing

detection on the mobile this is a hybrid model which combines diverse ML models for mobile phishing detection including feature fusion.

[15] Tanbhir, G., et al. (2025). Hybrid model which combines BERT and CNN that is a transfer method for phishing detection. It is useful for adapting BERT and handcrafted features together.

